

Chloromethylation of Some 5- and 6-Hydroxycoumarin Derivatives

S. S. Lele, N. G. Savant, and Suresh Sethna

5-Hydroxy- and 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarins and their methyl ethers and methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate have been chloromethylated using different molecular proportions of paraformaldehyde. Structures of the chloromethylated coumarins have been established by comparison of the methyl derivatives, obtained on reduction, with compounds of known structures.

The work on the chloromethylation of coumarins, described earlier (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, 25, 1713), has been extended.

Methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate on chloromethylation with one mole of paraformaldehyde furnished a monochloromethyl derivative, which on reduction gave methyl 5-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate, as seen on direct comparison with the compound synthesised as follows: 4-Methylresorcinol on carboxylation gave a monocarboxylic acid. This could either be 2,4-dihydroxy-5-methylbenzoic acid (A) or 2,6-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzoic acid (B). The methyl ester of (B) on the Pechmann condensation with ethyl acetoacetate would give a 7-hydroxycoumarin derivative. But the product actually obtained on the Pechmann condensation did not show any fluorescence, but gave a deep yellow solution with alkali, indicating that it was a 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative. The acid was therefore (A). Moreover, the Pechmann condensation product gave a deep reddish brown colour with ethanolic ferric chloride and so it was methyl 5-hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate and not the isomeric product, methyl 5-hydroxy-4,6-dimethylcoumarin-8-carboxylate. The monochloromethyl derivative is therefore methyl 5-hydroxy-8-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate.

Methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate on chloromethylation with an excess of paraformaldehyde furnished a dichloromethyl derivative, which must be methyl 5-hydroxy-3,8-dichloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate, as there was no other possibility. This on reduction gave the corresponding trimethyl derivative, which on hydrolysis, decarboxylation and methylation yielded 5-methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin.

5-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on chloromethylation furnished a polymeric product. Its methyl ether on similar chloromethylation with one mole of paraformaldehyde gave a pure but chlorine-free product. The analysis indicated its identity as a methylene-bis-(5-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin). It has not been investigated further.

5-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin on chloromethylation with an excess of paraformaldehyde furnished a dichloromethyl derivative. It was the 3,8-dichloromethyl derivative as on reduction it gave a product identical with 5-methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin, mentioned earlier.

6-Hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin on chloromethylation with 1 to 2 moles of paraformaldehyde furnishes a monochloromethyl derivative to which the 5-chloromethyl structure has been tentatively assigned as the product obtained from it on reduction is different from 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (Robertson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 2426) and 6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin. The latter was prepared by the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 4,7-dimethylcoumarin. Attempts to synthesise 6-hydroxy-4,5-dimethylcoumarin by the Clemmensen reduction of 6-hydroxy-5-formyl-4-methylcoumarin, prepared according to Naik and Thakor (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1957, 22, 1626), gave an unworkable product. The Sommelet reaction on the chloromethyl derivative gave a complex product. With an excess of paraformaldehyde 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin gave a polymeric product.

6-Methoxy-4-methylcoumarin on chloromethylation with 1 to 3 moles of paraformaldehyde did not give a pure product. On chloromethylation with excess of paraformaldehyde it gave the 3,7-dichloromethyl derivative, which on reduction gave 6-methoxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin, identical with the product obtained on methylation of 6-hydroxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin, prepared by the Elbs persulphate oxidation of 3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl 5-Hydroxy-8-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate.—A mixture of methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (4.68 g., 0.02M) in glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.), paraformaldehyde (0.72 g., 0.024M), and anhydrous zinc chloride (4.1 g., 0.03M) was heated on a steam bath and hydrogen chloride passed for 2 hours. The product separating was washed with ethanol and crystallised from benzene in colorless needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 215-17°. (Found: C, 55.2; H, 3.8; Cl, 12.7. $C_{13}H_{11}O_5Cl$ requires C, 55.2; H, 3.9; Cl, 12.6%).

Methyl 5-Hydroxy-4,8-dimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate.—The above chloromethylcoumarin (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (80%, 20 c.c.) was heated with zinc dust (1 g.) at 60-70° for 2 hours. The product separating on dilution with cold water was refluxed with benzene (10 c.c.). The insoluble portion crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 229°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 4.7. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.9%).

The same product was obtained when a mixture of methyl 2,4-dihydroxy-5-methylbenzoate (*vide infra*) (1.82 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (1.30 g.) was treated with 80% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.) and left overnight at room temperature. The product separating on pouring the reaction mixture in cold water was treated with sodium bicarbonate solution and the residue crystallised from rectified spirit.

2,4-Dihydroxy-5-methylbenzoic Acid.—A mixture of 4-methylresorcinol (10 g.), potassium bicarbonate (50 g.) and water (100 c.c.) was heated on a steam bath for 5 hours and then heated vigorously on a wire gauze for half an hour. The product separating on acidification was purified through sodium bicarbonate solution. It crystallised from hot water in shining yellow needles (4.5 g.), m.p. 212° (efferv.). (Found: C, 57.2; H, 4.8. $C_9H_8O_4$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8%).

* All melting points are uncorrected.

The *methyl ester*, prepared by refluxing the acid (10 g.) in methanol (50 c.c.) with H_2SO_4 (conc., 5 c.c.) for 10 hours, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether mixture in needles (8.0 g.), m.p. 122-24°. (Found: C, 59.1; H, 5.5. $C_9H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 59.3; H, 5.5%).

Methyl 5-Hydroxy-3,8-dichloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate.—A mixture of methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate (2.34 g., 0.01 *M*) in glacial acetic acid (60 c.c.), paraformaldehyde (4.8 g., 0.16*M*), and anhydrous zinc chloride (4.1 g.; 0.03*M*) was treated with hydrogen chloride at 100° for 1 hour. The product separating was washed with ethanol and crystallised from benzene in needles (2.2 g.), m.p. 168°. (Found: C, 50.7; H, 3.6; Cl, 21.1. $C_{14}H_{12}O_5Cl_2$ requires C, 50.8; H, 3.6; Cl, 21.5%).

The *diacetoxyethyl* derivative was prepared by refluxing the above chloromethylcoumarin in glacial acetic acid with fused sodium acetate for 2 hours. It crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 125-27°. (Found: C, 57.2; H, 4.9. $C_{15}H_{18}O_9$ requires C, 57.1; H, 4.8%).

Methyl 5-Hydroxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylate.—The above dichloromethyl derivative (1 g.) in acetic acid (80%, 40 c.c.) and zinc dust (2 g.) were heated at 60-70° for 2 hours. The product obtained on dilution with cold water was refluxed with benzene (5 c.c.) for 5 minutes and filtered. The residue was crystallised from acetic acid in shining needles, m.p. 218°. (Found: C, 64.2; H, 5.3. $C_{14}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 64.1; H, 5.3%).

5-Hydroxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The above ester (0.5 g.) was heated on a steam bath for 1 hour with 10% NaOH solution (10 c.c.). The product obtained on acidification was purified through sodium bicarbonate treatment and crystallised from dilute acetic acid, m.p. 274° (efferv.). (Found: C, 62.8; H 4.7. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.9; H 4.8%).

5-Hydroxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin.—The above acid (0.5 g.) in quinoline (10 c.c.) was refluxed on a sand bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour with a speck of copper powder. The mixture was filtered and added to HCl (dilute) solution. The separated product was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 246°. (Found: C, 70.0; H, 5.6. $C_{12}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%).

5-Methoxy-3,8-dichloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin.—A mixture of 5-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.9 g., 0.01*M*) in acetic acid (80%, 40 c.c.) and paraformaldehyde (2.4 g., 0.08*M*) was treated with HCl at 60-70° for 3 hours, and the mixture left overnight. The next day the separated solid was filtered and dried. It crystallised from benzene in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 173-75°. (Found: C, 53.9; H, 4.1; Cl, 24.6. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3Cl_2$ requires C, 54.4; H, 4.2; Cl, 24.7%).

The *diacetoxyethyl* derivative, prepared as before, crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 168-70°. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 5.2. $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 61.1; H, 5.4%).

5-Methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin.—The above dichloromethyl derivative (0.5 g.) was reduced by heating its solution in acetic acid (80 %, 20 c.c.) with zinc dust (1 g.) at 60-70° for 2 hours. The product obtained was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 198°. Mixed m.p. with 5-methoxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin, obtained by methylation of 5-hydroxy-3,4,8-trimethylcoumarin, described above, in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate as usual, was not depressed. (Found: C, 71.2; H, 6.4. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4%).

6-Hydroxy-5-chloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin.—A mixture of 6-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.76 g., 0.01M) in acetic acid (80%, 40 c.c.) and paraformaldehyde (0.3 g., 0.01M) was treated with HCl at 60-70° for 3 hours. The product separating on cooling was washed with ethanol and crystallised from dioxane in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 214°. (Found : C, 59.1; H, 4.0; Cl, 15.4. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl$ requires C, 58.8; H 4.1; Cl, 15.8%).

6-Hydroxy-4,5-dimethylcoumarin.—The above chloromethylcoumarin (0.5 g.) was heated with acetic acid (80 %, 10 c.c.) and zinc dust (1 g.) at 60-70° for 2 hours. The product separating on dilution with ice-cold water was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 225°. Mixed m.p. with 6-hydroxy-3,4-dimethylcoumarin (m.p. 236°) and 6-hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin, prepared as below (m.p. 208°), were depressed by about 20°. (Found : C, 69.3; H, 5.5. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 5.3).

6-Hydroxy-4,7-dimethylcoumarin.—4,7-Dimethylcoumarin (1 g.) was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution (40 c.c.) by warming on a steam bath. It was then oxidised with potassium persulphate (0.7 g. in 20 c.c. water) according to Parikh and Sethna (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 369). The product obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 208°. (Found : C, 69.5; H, 5.4. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 69.5; H, 5.3%) Desai and Mavani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 11), who prepared it by the Pechmann condensation of 2-methylhydroquinone and ethyl acetoacetate, reported the same m.p.

6-Methoxy-3,7-dichloromethyl-4-methylcoumarin.—A mixture of 6-methoxy-4-methylcoumarin (1.9 g., 0.01M) in glacial acetic acid (40 c.c.), paraformaldehyde (4.8 g., 0.16M), and anhydrous zinc chloride (2.72 g., 0.02M) was heated on a steam bath and dry HCl gas was passed for 3 hours. The product separating on cooling was washed with ethanol and crystallised from benzene in tiny buds (1.1 g.), m.p. 198-99°. (Found: C, 54.2; H, 4.4; Cl, 24.5. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3Cl_2$ requires C, 54.4; H, 4.2; Cl, 24.7%).

The *diacetoxyethyl* derivative, prepared as before, was crystallised from rectified spirit in needles, m.p. 162°. (Found : C, 61.2; H, 5.3. $C_{17}H_{18}O_7$ requires C, 61.1; H, 5.4%).

6-Methoxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin.—The above dichloromethylcoumarin (0.5 g.) in acetic acid (80%, 10 c.c.) was heated with zinc dust (1 g.) at 60-70° for 2 hours. The product obtained crystallised from dilute acetic acid in shining needles, m.p. 159°. Mixed m.p. with 6-methoxy 3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin, obtained by methylation of 6-hydroxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin which was prepared as below, was not depressed. (Found: C, 71.6; H, 6.5. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 71.6; H, 6.4%).

6-Hydroxy-3,4,7-trimethylcoumarin.—3,4,7-Trimethylcoumarin was oxidised with potassium persulphate according to Parikh and Sethna (*loc. cit.*). The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in needles, m.p. 273°. (Found: C, 70.2; H, 5.7. $C_{15}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.9%). Desai and Mavani (*loc. cit.*), who prepared it by the Pechmann condensation of 2-methylhydroquinone with ethyl α -methyl acetoacetate, reported m.p. 267°.